

EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL: DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF AN INTERACTIVE LEARNING MATERIAL FOR ENHANCING READING SKILLS IN FILIPINO I OF STO. CRISTO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Jhoan C. Aranas ¹, Jean Rose B. Rabano ¹, Harris Iñigo ²

¹*DepEd West, Sariaya, Quezon, Philippines*

²*CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc., Sariaya, Quezon, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14233364>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to enhance the reading comprehension skills of Grade One pupils in Filipino using interactive learning materials. The researcher conducted a descriptive method of research, specifically through survey research to determine the significant difference between the evaluation of teacher and students on the developed interactive learning material in Filipino 1 in Sto. Cristo Elementary School. The respondents of this study were 6 Grade I teachers and 182 Grade I students enrolled in S.Y. 2023-2024. The researcher used total enumeration in this study. According to Sugiyono (2014:68), total population sampling is a sampling approach in which the entire population is treated as a sample. The researcher used weighted mean of the score in the pretest to identify the least learned competencies in Filipino I. Frequency and percentage distribution employed to assess the students' comprehension levels in Filipino before and after the utilization of ILMs, as well as the teachers' evaluations of the ILMs' accuracy, relevance, and appropriateness for Filipino I. The significant relationship between the level of comprehension of the students before and after the use of ILM's in Filipino compared using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). Based on the findings, the respondents' level of reading comprehension skills was very satisfactory before the use of interactive learning materials and outstanding after the use. The respondents' evaluation strongly agreed on the accuracy, relevance, and appropriateness of interactive learning materials. There is significant difference between the level of comprehension skills of the students before and after the utilization of ILM's in Filipino I. There is no significant relationship of evaluation of teachers to the result of

pretest and posttest.

Keywords: *Interactive learning materials, reading comprehension, pretest, posttest*

INTRODUCTION

One important educational objective that supports children's achievement is learning to read. Proficiency in reading is highly regarded and crucial for personal growth. Everyone will benefit from having this skill since it will enable us to read literature, learn new things, and go about our daily lives.

The four macro skills are speaking, writing, listening, and reading. Reading is one of the difficult abilities on the list because so many pupils remain able to get better at it. When reading, comprehension of even a single word's meaning is necessary in order to comprehend the text we will be reading.

According to Nicolielo-Carrilho et al., (2018), cognitive processes involved in reading include several others, starting with word and letter recognition. Word recognition involves recognizing familiar words by sight without having to sound them out, whereas letter recognition involves the ability to identify individual letters and the sounds they make. These skills are essential for developing reading fluency, comprehension, and writing skills. Also, cognitive processes work together to enable fluent reading and comprehension. If cognitive processes are disrupted, it can lead to reading difficulties and challenges. Mammarella et al., (2014) added that reading issues may cause serious risks and have an impact on future learning if they are not recognized and treated in the early stages of school. If these issues are not treated properly, they can lead to reading difficulties, which can impact a person's academic and professional success.

As stated by Arciuli, (2018), since reading helps children learn and enriches their lives, it is an essential educational skill, especially given the need for strong reading foundations in primary school Zhao, Song, Zhao & Zhang, (2018). In addition, teachers need to prepare for assessments such diagnostic tests when a student has difficulty with reading and writing Łodygowska, Chęć & Samochowiec, (2017). Students who have difficulty in reading may experience emotional effects such as low self-esteem and issues with their academic performance Novita, (2016).

Moreover, for success or learning outcomes in both school and society, reading comprehension is portrayed as one of the most crucial skills and a complex cognitive process where the reader's prior experiences and knowledge play a crucial role in the interpretation of a text or the interaction between the reader, the text, and the context. A number of cognitive and linguistic abilities are required for reading comprehension, which is a challenging task. Because of this, deficiencies in any cognitive skill critical to the comprehension process may result in poor reading comprehension performance. In order to extract information or ideas from printed material, reading is a passive skill that necessitates a participatory comprehension process. The definition of reading ability,

which includes the capacity to read from a variety of specialists with divergent points of view, must be understood by reading teachers. It would be helpful to know how to teach reading in the classroom and a fantastic resource for learning more about how to deal with reading skills in general.

According to Kendeou et al., (2016), one of the most challenging and significant cognitive tasks that people carry out is reading comprehension. Additionally, reading comprehension is a crucial ability that might affect the learning outcome and ongoing language development Babapour et al., (2018).

In terms of reading comprehension proficiency among Asian nations, China comes out on top, followed by Singapore. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2018) of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) found that the Philippines scored the lowest in reading comprehension among Asian nations. The reading comprehension issue in the Philippines, as evidenced by the PISA 2018 results, is nothing new. According to data from the Department of Education from 2007, 70% of children's reading abilities are below grade level. Additionally, a Philippine Star story from 2011 claims that Filipinos lack drive and adequate reading skills. Additionally, it was noted in the study by Cabardo (2015) that pupils' poor performance on the National Achievement Test was a sign of their poor reading comprehension abilities. Learning and mastering the Filipino language require the development of a variety of macro-skills, including speaking, reading, writing, and listening. Reading is also the most important academic skill among the macro-skills. Even while reading plays a significant part in learning, some children still struggle with it.

Furthermore, interactive resources created to teach a certain learning result are known as interactive learning materials. They could consist of one or more pages with any mix of text, graphics, audio, and video, including screencasts, animations, questions for a self-test, and other interactive features.

As stated by Ahmed & Nasser, (2015) due to their upbringing around digital gadgets as a cultural norm, the majority of the young, knowledgeable about technology generation is predisposed to digital literacy.

Also, the media environment has been significantly altered by the internet, and graphic animations can now be used to construct multimedia stories for education that also include text, video, image, and audio Van Krieken, (2018). Moreover, Bus et al., (2014) cited that animated images are enhanced by music and audio, which are also used to present tales that combine words with nonverbal information to improve comprehension. Thus, multimedia has significantly improved the reading habits of underachieving students. Underachievers are given the chance to continue their education in accordance with their unique demands and intelligence.

Given the foregoing assumptions, the researcher desires to assist teachers and students in learning how to read and comprehend easily by using interactive learning materials as a primary tool in improving comprehension skills in Filipino. Due to the

illiteracy problem, this will help to improve literacy rates using compendium of interactive learning materials that teachers may use in teaching language and developing ability to comprehend in Filipino.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the development and evaluation of interactive learning material in Filipino I in reading comprehension in Sto. Cristo Elementary School.

Specifically, the study aimed to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the process of development of the interactive learning material?
2. What is the level of reading comprehension skills of the students before and after utilization of interactive learning materials?
3. What is the evaluation of Filipino teachers in interactive learning materials in terms of:
 - 3.1. accuracy;
 - 3.2. relevance;
 - 3.3. and appropriateness?
4. Is there significant difference between the level of comprehension skills of the students before and after the utilization of ILM's in Filipino I?
5. Is there significant relationship of evaluation of teachers to the result of pretest and post test?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

The researcher conducted a descriptive method of research, specifically through survey research to determine the significant difference between the evaluation of teacher and students on the developed interactive learning material in Filipino 1 in Sto. Cristo Elementary School. In this design, researcher used pretest to determine the least learned in Filipino I. The researcher adapted a survey questionnaire for the evaluation of the material from the study of Jonalyn L. Sulit, 2023 from the study Development and Evaluation of an Interactive Learning Material in Reading For English 8. The survey method is a technique for gathering data for the purpose of research by asking respondents about the study.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Sto. Cristo Elementary School. It is located at Sto. Cristo Sariaya, Quezon. The respondents of this study were 6 Grade I teachers and 182 Grade I students enrolled in S.Y. 2023-2024. The researcher used total enumeration in this study. According to Sugiyono (2014:68), total population sampling is a sampling approach in which the entire population was treated as a sample.

Research Instrument

The researcher created a 25-item test with the goal of evaluating participants' pre-existing comprehension skills in Filipino in a way that was consistent with their subject-area competencies. The pretest's response format is multiple-choice. The researcher asked for three Master teachers teaching in the same school to validate the content of the questionnaire before administering it. After knowing the results, the researcher developed a set of interactive learning materials that focused on improving comprehension skills in Filipino 1. These materials can include interactive videos, online exercises, multimedia presentations, or any other form of engaging content that promotes comprehension skills development. After the participants have used the interactive learning materials for a specific period, the researcher administered a post-test questionnaire to evaluate the impact of these materials on their comprehension skills. To evaluate the interactive learning materials, the researcher adapted questionnaires from the Jonalyn L. Sulit 2023 study.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher sent a letter to the division office and district office to conduct the study. The researcher also composed a letter addressed to the school principal, explaining the purpose and objectives of the study. The researcher requested permission to conduct the research within the school premises and ask for the necessary data needed for the study, assured the principal that all materials required for the study will be provided by the researcher and emphasized that the research activities were not disrupt regular classes or cause any inconvenience to the school. The researcher asked the Grade 1 advisers to provide the researcher with the numbers and names of the Grade 1 students and ensure that the privacy and confidentiality of the students' information are maintained. The researcher scheduled a meeting with the Grade 1 advisers to explain the research procedures and their role in the study, clearly outline how to conduct the pretest and post-test using the provided questionnaires and explained how to implement the use of interactive learning materials as part of regular classroom activities.

The researcher provided the Grade 1 advisers with survey questionnaires to evaluate the effectiveness of the interactive learning materials and emphasized the importance of honest and unbiased responses to gather accurate feedback. In data collection the researcher collected the pretest and post-test questionnaires, ensuring all necessary data was obtained from the Grade 1 students. The researcher analyzed the collected data using appropriate statistical methods to determine the impact of the interactive learning materials on the students' comprehension skills and presented the

findings of the study in a clear and organized manner, ensuring that the results address the research objectives.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher tallied, analyzed, and statistically treated the data to evaluate the responses of the respondents and determine significant difference between the evaluation of teacher and students on the developed interactive learning material in Filipino I. The researcher used weighted mean of the score in the pretest to identify the least learned competencies in Filipino I. Frequency and percentage distribution employed to assess the students' comprehension levels in Filipino before and after the utilization of ILMs, as well as the teachers' evaluations of the ILMs' accuracy, relevance, and appropriateness for Filipino I. The significant relationship between the level of comprehension of the students before and after the use of ILM's in Filipino compared using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r).

RESULTS

This part of the study gives the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from the questionnaires answered by the respondents. Such presentation is in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

1. What is the process of development of the interactive learning material?

Interactive learning material is often developed using a structured procedure to verify its efficacy and alignment with learning objectives. During the analysis step, the instructional designer determines the aims and objectives of the learning materials. This entails understanding the target audience, their traits, and their current knowledge levels. A needs assessment is used to identify the gap between existing knowledge and desired learning goals. By studying these elements, the designer can develop a plan for interactive learning materials that effectively answer the specified demands. The design stage entails organizing the information and activities in a manner that supports the learning objectives. Instructional techniques are used to interest students and aid in knowledge retention. The design stage is critical in producing a coherent and successful learning experience for the students. During the development stage, the actual interactive learning content is created according to the design criteria. Content is written, multimedia elements are developed and incorporated, and interactive features are programmed. Simulations, quizzes, and films are examples of tools that can be created to improve the learning experience. This step necessitates careful attention to detail to ensure that the material performs as planned and satisfies the learning objectives. Implementation entails making the material available to students and giving the appropriate instructions for their use. The evaluation stage entails determining the efficacy of the interactive learning content. Teachers provide feedback to help identify strengths and areas for improvement. Learning outcomes are examined to assess whether the information met its intended

objectives. Based on the evaluation results, adjustments may be made to improve the material's quality and efficacy for future usage.

By following these steps - analyze, design, develop, implement, and evaluate - the creation of interactive learning material can result in a well-structured and interesting learning experience for students.

2. Level of Reading Comprehension Skills of the Students Before and After Utilization of Interactive Learning Materials.

Table 1

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills of the Students Before the Utilization of Interactive Learning Materials

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
20 - 25 (Outstanding)	63	34.62	2
15 - 19 (Very satisfactory)	92	50.55	1
10 - 14 (Satisfactory)	27	14.83	3
Total	182	100	
Mean Score	17.92 (Very Satisfactory)		
Standard Deviation	3.29 (Dispersed)		

As seen in Table 1, the very satisfactory scores of 15 - 19 gained the highest frequency count of 92 or 50.55% at rank 1 while the satisfactory score of 10 - 14 got the least frequency count of 27 or 14.83% at rank 3.

The mean score was 17.92 described as very satisfactory and the standard deviation was 3.29. These implied that majority of the pupil-respondents performed very satisfactorily in their pretest in Filipino. The scores were also dispersed compared to the post test results. The statement implies that a large proportion of the pupils tested received high marks in their first evaluation in the Filipino subject. This shows that the majority of the pupil-respondents performed well on the pretest for Filipino.

Table 2

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills of the Students After the Utilization of Interactive Learning Materials

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
20 - 25 (Outstanding)	101	55.49	1
15 - 19 (Very satisfactory)	76	41.76	2
10 - 14 (Satisfactory)	5	2.75	3
Total	182	100	
Mean Score	19.59 (Outstanding)		
Standard Deviation	2.52 (Compressed)		

As gleaned in table 2, the outstanding scores of 20 - 25 obtained the highest frequency count of 101 or 55.49 % at rank 1 whereas the satisfactory scores of 10 - 14 made the least frequency count of five or 2.75 % at rank 3. The mean score was 19.59 rated as outstanding and the standard deviation was 2.52. These affirmed that the majority of the pupil-respondents performed outstandingly after the utilization of Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino. The scores were also compressed compared to the pre test results. It implies that during the post test the respondent performed outstandingly as compared to the result in their pre test. In the study of Husain (2014), claimed that the usage of interactive media, particularly in presentations, has a significant impact and is effective in improving student learning results.

3. Evaluation of Filipino Teachers in Interactive Learning Materials.

3.1. In Terms of Accuracy.

Table 3

Evaluation of Filipino Teachers in Interactive Learning Materials

In Terms of Accuracy

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1 The content of the reading material is according to topics presented in K-12 Curriculum Guide for Grade 1 Filipino.	4.00	Strongly Agree	3

2 The content is congruent with the objectives and desired learning competencies.	4.00	Strongly Agree	3
3 The reading material has organized tasks within the abilities and skills of the students.	4.00	Strongly Agree	3
4 The reading material conveys simple and understandable instructions.	4.00	Strongly Agree	3
5 The reading material uses words that are within the students' level of comprehension.	4.00	Strongly Agree	3
Composite Mean	4.00	Strongly Agree	

As given in Table 3, the teacher respondents strongly agreed that the content of the reading material is according to topics presented in K-12 Curriculum Guide for Grade 1 Filipino, that the content is congruent with the objectives and desired learning competencies, that the reading material has organized tasks within the abilities and skills of the students, that the reading material conveys simple and understandable instructions, and that the reading material uses words that are within the students' level of comprehension with the highest obtained weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 3. In addition, the reading material gives clear and easy directions in language that students can understand. According to Cronbac (2015), as mentioned by Inyang (2022), the use of instructional materials during the teaching and learning process can attract students' attention and generate interest, allowing the learner to attain the intended objective.

The composite mean of 4.00 assessed that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the accuracy of the Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino. The significance of accuracy in interactive learning materials comes from its important role in shaping students' comprehension, critical thinking abilities, and readiness for future academic and professional endeavors. As a result, guaranteeing the accuracy of content in interactive learning materials is critical for delivering a high-quality and effective learning experience. In the study of Funcion (2019) instructional materials are critical in the teaching and learning process. Based on the findings of her research, it was discovered that while developing instructional materials, the content is centered on the student needs and in accuracy with the course objectives in the syllabus.

3.2. In Terms of Relevance.

Table 4

**Evaluation of Filipino Teachers in Interactive Learning Materials
In Terms of Relevance**

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1 The reading material reflects the kind of environment students are exposed with.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
2 The reading material is in-line with the K-12 Curriculum Guide for Grade 1 Filipino.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
3 The reading material presents adequate and understandable information relevant to students' knowledge.	3.67	Strongly Agree	5
4 The reading material exemplifies objectives stated in the K-12 Curriculum Guide for Grade 1 Filipino.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
5 The reading material provides tasks that target the desired learning outcomes and competencies set for Grade 1 Filipino.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
Composite Mean	3.93	Strongly Agree	

As seen in Table 4, the teacher respondents strongly agreed that the reading material reflects the kind of environment students are exposed with, that the reading material is in-line with the K-12 Curriculum Guide for Grade 1 Filipino, that the reading material exemplifies objectives stated in the K-12 Curriculum Guide for Grade 1 Filipino, and that the reading material provides tasks that target the desired learning outcomes and competencies set for Grade 1 Filipino with the highest obtained weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 2.5. It implies that reading material acts as a catalyst for engaging students, increasing the productivity of teaching and learning, providing valuable knowledge sources, broadening human experiences, and creating a more concrete, authentic, and immediate learning environment. According to Akintunde and Danlami (2018), instructional materials enhance learning by stimulating interest,

increasing productivity, providing relevant knowledge, broadening human experience, and providing tangible learning opportunities.

On the other hand, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that The reading material presents adequate and understandable information relevant to students' knowledge which got the least weighted mean of 3.67 and least rank of 5. The reading material efficiently communicates comprehensive and accessible information that is customized to the students' level of comprehension. It guarantees that the information is both adequate and relevant for improving pupils' understanding. According to Evuti & Ali (2020), instructional materials are collections of relevant and diverse resources used to improve classroom communication and learning.

The composite mean of 3.93 affirmed that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the relevance of the Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino. Overall, relevance needs to be done in interactive learning materials to personalize the learning experience, increase engagement and motivation, promote real-world application, align with learning outcomes, fulfill learner requirements, and maximize resource utilization. By guaranteeing relevance, educators may deliver meaningful and effective learning experiences that help students learn and succeed. As stated by Hibek (2015) the relevance of instructional materials are utilized as remediation for students who struggle with their classes. These materials include topics, discussions, and visuals that provide additional knowledge related to specific lectures.

Interactive learning materials must be relevant to interest students and improve their learning experience. When interactive resources are closely relevant to the subject matter being taught, students are more likely to remain focused, motivated, and engaged in the learning process. Relevance in interactive learning materials enables students to make meaningful connections between the content and their personal experiences, prior knowledge, and interests. This relationship not only strengthens their understanding of the subject, but it also improves their overall retention and application of knowledge. Furthermore, when students realize the connection between the interactive learning materials and actual situations or potential career opportunities, they are more likely to invest in the learning process and be encouraged to succeed. Using appropriate interactive resources, teachers can create a more interesting and effective learning environment that maximizes student engagement, comprehension, and retention.

3.3. In Terms of Appropriateness.

Table 5

**Evaluation of Filipino Teachers in Interactive Learning Materials
In Terms of Appropriateness**

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1.The reading material elicits active participation of the students from class discussions.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
2 The reading material enables the students to develop his/he critical and analytical thinking.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
3. The reading material serves as new learning materials in Filipino 1.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
4. The provided activities in each lesson are presented with clear directions and appropriate with the ability of the students	3.83	Strongly Agree	5
5 The reading material is easy to understand by the students.	4.00	Strongly Agree	2.5
Composite Mean	3.97	Strongly Agree	

As written in Table 5, the teacher respondents strongly agreed that the reading material elicits active participation of the students from class discussions, that the reading material enables the students to develop his/he critical and analytical thinking, that the reading material serves as new learning materials in Filipino 1, and that the reading material is easy to understand by the students which made the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 2.5. Overall, the high ratings and rankings of the reading material in these areas indicate that the teachers view it as a highly effective resource for promoting student engagement, critical thinking, and comprehension in the context of Filipino 1. According to Castillo (2021) cited Dodd's (2015) research, which stated that additional resources excite learners by boosting enthusiasm in studying and motivating them to use the language in class and develop active participation.

Furthermore, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that the provided activities in each lesson are presented with clear directions and appropriate with the ability of the students which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.83 and least rank of 5. The

respondents' strong agreement in these areas suggests that the reading material effectively delivers clear and relevant activities to assist student learning and engagement. By providing well-structured and appropriate tasks, the content improves students' comprehension and helps them to actively participate in the learning process. Based on Hjetland et al., (2019) students who are uninterested in the reading material will get demotivated. As a result, the reading content chosen affects students' motivation and reading abilities.

The composite mean of 3.97 proved that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the appropriateness of the Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino. Materials can be customized to cater diverse learning styles and abilities, making the learning process more inclusive and effective for all students. Degeng (2013) claimed that the choice of learning media is directly related to learning objectives. Learning media and resources should be compatible and appropriate.

4. Difference Between the Level of Comprehension Skills of the Students Before and After the Utilization of ILM's in Filipino I.

Table 6

Difference Between the Level of Comprehension Skills of the Students Before and After the Utilization of ILM's in Filipino I

Variable	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pre Versus Post Tests	5.57	9.97E-8	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

As presented in Table 6, the computed t-value of 5.57 for pre test versus post test scores has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

This safely concluded that the pretest scores before the utilization of Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino have high significant differences with the scores after the utilization of the said learning material. Furthermore, compared to the pre-test results, the utilization of Interactive Learning Materials improved the students' performance. According to Tekerek & Tekerek (2018), interactive learning materials serve as a teaching tool. In other words, it is a useful tool for teaching concepts from different domains through integrating them.

This also generalized that the utilization of Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino was very effective. This implies that the interactive materials had a positive impact on the learning process and outcomes in the comprehension skills in Filipino I. Based on Tety (2016) effective utilization of instructional resources in the classroom is essential for teaching and learning. Instructional materials give teachers tools to improve learning and retention.

5. Relationship Between the Evaluation of Teachers to the Result of Pretest and Post test.

Table 7

Relationship Between the Evaluation of Teachers to the Result of Pretest and Post test

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pre and Post Test Results versus Evaluation of Teachers in ILM:				
Accuracy	0.00	1.00000	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Relevance	0.01	0.89342	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Appropriateness	0.08	0.28303	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

As gleaned in Table 7, when the evaluation of the teachers on the Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino were compared to the pre and post test scores of the pupils, the computed r-values of 0.00 for accuracy, 0.01 for relevance and 0.08 for appropriateness have corresponding p-values of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These inferred that the evaluation of the teachers on the Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino in terms of accuracy, relevance and appropriateness have no significant relationships to the pre and post test scores of the pupils. This means that how teachers assess the quality and suitability of the materials does not have a noticeable impact on the students' test scores before and after using these materials. The lack of correlation between teacher evaluation and student achievement suggests that factors other than perceived quality of materials may have an impact on the effectiveness of Interactive Learning Materials in Filipino. These could include students' prior knowledge, levels of involvement, learning environment, and instructional approaches.

As a result, even if teachers give the Interactive Learning Materials high marks for accuracy, relevance, and appropriateness, there is no guarantee that students' test scores would improve directly. The success of these materials in improving student learning outcomes may be determined by a variety of measures other than teacher evaluation. According to Akintunde and Danlami (2018), learning materials improve learning through creating interest, boosting productivity, giving relevant knowledge, broadening human experience, and making learning more concrete, real, and immediate, among other advantages.

Conclusions

Based on the findings as summarized, the following were concluded: 1) The respondents' level of reading comprehension skills was very satisfactory before the use of interactive learning materials and outstanding after the use. The use of interactive learning materials resulted in a significant improvement in the respondents' reading comprehension skills, moving them from a very satisfactory to an outstanding level. This demonstrates the effectiveness of utilizing interactive learning tools in improving reading comprehension outcomes. 2) The respondents' evaluation was strongly agreed on the accuracy, relevance and appropriateness of interactive learning materials. Respondents overwhelmingly agreed that the interactive learning materials used were accurate, relevant, and acceptable. This collective positive evaluation highlights the effectiveness and alignment of the interactive materials with their educational needs and goals. 3) There is significant difference between the level of comprehension skills of the students before and after the utilization of ILM's in Filipino I. This observable difference demonstrates the significant impact of interactive learning tools on improving students' comprehension skills. 4) There is no significant relationship of evaluation of teachers to the result of pretest and posttest. This suggests that the evaluation of teachers does not have an observable impact on the performance of the students in the pretest and posttest assessments.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Sustaining parental engagement in school activities is essential, alongside the encouragement of school-initiated programs that facilitate increased participation of parents/guardians. This collaborative approach fosters a synergistic relationship in delivering educational services and contributes to the attainment of elevated learning outcomes.
2. It is advisable for the school to consistently formulate strategic measures aimed at upholding high performance in areas such as enrolment, promotion, retention, graduation rates, and the reduction of drop-out rates, with the active involvement and support of both internal and external stakeholders. This collaborative effort ensures the ongoing enhancement of educational outcomes and the sustained success of the institution.
3. While acknowledging the significance of parental engagement, it's important to recognize that it may not singularly dictate educational metrics. Therefore, there is a need for further research to delve into additional variables that potentially impact student progress. Emphasizing the multifaceted nature of academic success, such investigations can provide a more comprehensive understanding, informing strategies that effectively support students in achieving their educational goals.

4. Collaboration between the school and parents is crucial in cultivating a supportive and conducive environment for student advancement and success throughout their educational journey. Emphasizing the significance of effective educational strategies and support mechanisms within this partnership is essential. By working together, both parties can enhance student learning experiences and facilitate their overall academic achievement.
5. Encouraging collaboration between schools and parents is paramount in achieving educational outcomes for students at both elementary and secondary levels. This collaborative effort should aim to enhance various educational indicators, reflecting a conducive environment for high student progression, retention, and success. Such outcomes underscore the effectiveness of existing educational strategies and support systems, emphasizing the importance of continued partnership between schools and parents in promoting student achievement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To make this study ethically acceptable, the following points provided importance during data collection:

- Consent was requested from every potential participant.
- Participants in the study's privacy was protected.
- An appropriate degree of anonymity and confidentiality were maintained when handling data.

In general, the researcher must be ethical so that the respondent will not suffer physical harm, discomfort, pain, embarrassment, or loss of privacy.

Acknowledgments

The researcher wishes to express his heartfelt gratitude and appreciation to those who have become instrumental in the realization of this study. Deserving special mentions are:

To Dr. Jean Rose B. Rabano, thesis adviser, for her support, counsel, guidance, important remarks, recommendations, and provisions that greatly aided the completion and accomplishment of this study. She also provided love, care, and shelter during the thesis process. Sharing her skills and helping with data analysis. Finally, by providing an unending assisting mind to complete this manuscript.

To the panel members, Dr. Orbel M. Canoy, Dr. Lino P. Balantac, and Fr. Harris I. Garcia, for their insightful remarks, suggestions, and recommendations to improve this study, as well as approval and excellent recognition.

To her statistician, Dr. Lino P. Balantac, for his hard work in the statistical treatment of the research and supporting her in the interpretation and analysis of the data.

To Mr. Rommel C. Bautista CESO V, Schools Division Superintendent, for allowing her to conduct this study in Sto. Cristo Elementary School, Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon.

To Ms. Maria Lourdes C. Cabanag, Sariaya West Public Schools District Supervisor, Mr. Reynaldo D. Luces Jr., Sto. Cristo Elementary School Principal III, and to the advisers of the respondents, for giving their full support and cooperation in the data gathering process.

To the respondents of the study, for their valuable time and cooperation in acquiring the necessary data for the study, as well as their valuable responds and ideas that assist the researcher to generate accurate findings and appropriate output.

To Jeric D. Aranas, her husband, for the love, encouragement, support, and sacrifices throughout this study.

To Xyv Keiden C. Aranas, her son, the researcher's source of happiness, motivation, and inspiration.

Most importantly, the God Almighty for the countless blessings, guidance, strength, and insight that help the researcher to accomplish the study.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, S. (2017). Authentic ELT materials in the language classroom: An overview. *Journal of applied linguistics and language research*, 4(2), 181-202.
- Arciuli, J. (2018). Reading as statistical learning. *Language Speech and Hearing Services in Schools*, 49(3S), 634–643. https://doi.org/10.1044/2018_lshss-stlt1-17-0135
- Cabardo, J. R. (2015). Reading Proficiency Level of Students: Basis for Reading Intervention Program. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2712237>
- Hjetland, H. N., Lervåg, A., Lyster, S.-A. H., Hagtvet, B. E., Hulme, C., & Melby-Lervåg, M. (2019). Pathways to reading comprehension: A longitudinal study from 4 to 9 years of age. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(5), 751–763. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000321>
- Kendeou, P., Van Den Broek, P., Helder, A., & Karlsson, J. (2014). A Cognitive View of Reading Comprehension: Implications for reading Difficulties. *Learning Disabilities Research and Practice*, 29(1), 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ldrp.12025>
- Mammarella, V., Arigliani, E., Giovannone, F., Cavalli, G., Tofani, M., & Sogos, C. (2022). Is it hyperlexia? Toward a deeper understanding of precocious reading skills in two cases of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. *PubMed*, 173(1), 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.7417/ct.2022.2385>
- Nicolielo-Carrilho, A. P., Crenitte, P. A. P., Lopes-Herrera, S. A. & Hage, S. R. De V. (2018). Relationship between phonological working memory, meta cognitive skills and reading comprehension in children with learning disabilities. *Journal of Applied Oral Science*, 26, 1-8.
- OECD (2019), *The Road to Integration: Education and Migration*, OECD Reviews of Migrant Education, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1787/d8ceec5d-en>
- PISA 2018 Assessment and Analytical Framework. (2019, April 26). OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/pisa-2018-assessment-and-analytical->

framework_b25efab8-en.html

Zhao, W., Song, Y., Zhao, Q., & Zhang, R. (2018). The effect of teacher support on primary school students' reading engagement: the mediating role of reading interest and chinese academic self-concept. *Educational Psychology*, 39(2), 236–253. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2018.1497146>
